

Non-Performing Loan (NPL) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the NPL ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the NPL ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the NPL ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 750 journal publications regarding the NPL ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the NPL ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 1 89 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 47 topics around the influence of the NPL ratio and 47 topics about the determinants of the NPL ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around NPL ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Non-Performing Loan (NPL), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

As the banking industry advances and the public's demand for credit increases, credit risk becomes increasingly important in banking operations. Non-Performing Loan (NPL) Ratio is one of the most important indicators of a bank's financial health and is most often used by regulators and investors to assess the quality of a bank's credit portfolio. The NPL ratio is calculated by dividing the number of unpaid loans by the total loans provided by the bank. For example, if a bank has a loan of IDR 1 trillion and IDR 100 billion of it is not paid, then the NPL ratio is 10%. A high NPL ratio indicates that the bank is experiencing financial problems and has the potential to suffer large losses. Meanwhile, a low NPL ratio indicates good credit portfolio quality and the bank's ability to manage credit risk well. Therefore, the NPL ratio is very important for banks and regulators to ensure that banks can survive in the long term.

In recent years, technological developments and financial innovation have brought changes to the banking industry. Some banks have used technology to collect and analyze credit data more efficiently, allowing them to better monitor their credit portfolios. This can help reduce credit risk and improve the bank's NPL ratio. In addition, several countries have also introduced new regulations to ensure that banks can manage credit risks well. For example, some countries require banks to place reserve funds to cover losses due to NPLs. This can help reduce credit risk and strengthen the bank's financial health.

In Indonesia, the Financial Services Authority (OJK) has regulations regarding the NPL ratio limits permitted for banks. Currently, the NPL ratio limit permitted for conventional banks is 5%, while for sharia banks it is 3%. OJK also carries out routine checks on banks to ensure that their NPL ratios remain within permitted limits. Overall, the use of the NPL ratio in banking continues to grow in line with developments in the banking industry and existing regulations. The NPL ratio remains one of the main indicators of a bank's financial health and will continue to be closely monitored by regulators and investors in the future. Therefore, banks must ensure that they manage credit risks well and maintain the NPL ratio within permitted limits to maintain their financial health.

The development of research on NPLs in banking has become an important topic in economic and financial literature. The following are several examples of research developments related to NPLs in banking: first, research that explores the factors that influence NPLs in banks, including macroeconomic factors, banking characteristics, and internal factors such as risk management and credit policy. The results of this research can help banks better identify and manage credit risks. Second, research that evaluates the impact of NPLs on bank financial performance, including their effect on profitability, liquidity and capital suitability. The results of this research can help banks assess their performance and take appropriate action to improve their financial health. Third, research that evaluates the influence of government regulations and policies on NPLs in banking. The results of this research can help regulators in designing effective regulations to reduce credit risk and strengthen bank financial health. Fourth, research that evaluates credit risk management practices in banks, including credit analysis processes, credit portfolio management, and non-performing credit risk management. The results of this research can help banks develop better credit risk management practices. Fifth, research that explores the use of technology such as data analysis and artificial intelligence in managing credit risk and reducing NPLs. The results of this research can help banks develop more effective technological solutions to overcome NPL problems. Overall, the development of research on NPLs in banking continues to grow along with developments in the banking industry and financial innovation. This research is very important for banks and regulators to ensure that credit risk can be managed well and the bank's financial health can be maintained in the long term.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around NPLs in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding NPL. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research NPL matters. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can identify research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Non-Performing Loan (NPL) or bad credit is a term used in the banking industry to describe credit that has matured and is unable to be met by the borrower, so that the bank cannot collect repayment for the principal amount and interest owed. In simpler terms, NPL can be defined as credit that cannot be repaid by the party who borrows it, and therefore becomes a problem for the bank or financial institution that provides it. If a bank's NPL amount is too high, this could cause the bank to suffer financial losses, and ultimately could threaten the stability of the banking industry as a whole. Therefore, the NPL level is an important indicator in assessing the health and performance of a bank.

Bibliometric studies are research methods that use bibliographic data to measure and analyze the characteristics of scientific publications. This method involves collecting bibliographic data from scientific publications, such as journals, articles, books, etc., and then performing statistical analysis on the data. The main goal of a bibliometric study is to measure the impact and influence of scientific publications and evaluate the productivity and research quality of an individual, group, or institution. Several aspects that can be measured through bibliometric studies include publication frequency, most productive authors, distribution of research topics, collaboration networks between researchers, and the impact of publications, such as citation indexes. This method has been used in a variety of disciplines, including science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and humanities, and can assist researchers, publishers, and academic institutions in making strategic decisions about research and management of scientific publications.

VOSviewer is one of the software or software used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data, such as co-citation, co-authorship, bibliographic data couplings, and so on. This software

was developed by Leiden University and can be downloaded for free. VOSviewer allows users to analyze and visualize bibliometric data in the form of a network map. The network map shows the relationship between elements in bibliometric data, such as the relationship between authors, research topics, journals, etc. In VOSviewer, users can customize the appearance of network maps and explore bibliometric data using various analysis tools, such as clustering, factor analysis, and path analysis. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, publishers and academic institutions in analyzing and visualizing bibliometric data, as well as making strategic decisions about research and management of scientific publications.

Studies Literature review is a form of research carried out to compile and evaluate literature related to a particular topic in a scientific discipline. The primary goal of a literature review study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of a research topic, including the history, trends, and controversies within the field. Literature review studies usually involve collecting, evaluating, and synthesizing literature relevant to a research topic from various sources, such as journals, books, and conference articles. The researcher then evaluates and analyzes the literature to find conclusions or conclusions that can be drawn about the research topic. Literature review studies can be conducted as independent research or as part of wider research. Literature review studies can be used in various disciplines, including science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and humanities. This method helps researchers to understand trends and changes in their research, identify research areas that need development, and develop a strong theoretical framework for their research.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Non-Performing Loans (NPL). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on NPLs in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Non-Performing Loan " and " NPL " throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding NPL using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around NPL using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around NPL using a literature review study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications Regarding Non-Performing Loans (NPL) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 750 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2006 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding NPL by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2006	2	2013	30	2019	72

2008	1	2014	40	2020	87
2009	1	2015	57	2021	88
2010	2	2016	59	2022	116
2011	4	2017	75	2023	13
2012	11	2018	92		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Mapping Regarding Non-Performing Loans (NPL) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around NPL. Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research map regarding the NPL ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 4 clusters and 189 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 69 topic items, namely: analytical method, annual report, bad credit, bad loan, bank, bank Indonesia, state savings bank, banking sector, bi rate, business, condition, conventional bank, conventional commercial, covid, credit distribution, credit risk, customer, data analysis technique, data collection technique, debtor, deposit, distribution, economy, effort, exchange rate, external factor, financial institution/intermediary/performance, form, fund, gdp, gross domestic product, growth, health, inflation, inflation, influence, interest rate, internal factor, interview, mortgage, lending, level, lpd, negative effect, non-performing loan, npls, party, path analysis, performance, company, person, positive effect, problem, PT Bank Mandiri, PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia, quantitative approach/method, relationship, research method/result, risk, role, secondary data, significant influence, tbk, technique.
- Cluster 2, consists of 57 topic items, namely: analysis method/technique, autocorrelation test, bank profitability, banking company, bopo, bpr, classical assumption test,

coefficient, commercial bank, company, cost, criteria, determination, earnings, effect, expense, f test, financial ratio/services authority/statement, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, idx, income, insignificant effect, net interest margin, nim, normality test, npl bopo, ojk, operating income, operational costs, population, profit, profitability, purposive sampling method, regression, research period/sample, rest, rural bank, sampling technique, significance level, significant effect/impact/negative effect/positive effect, size, stock exchange, stock price, t test, variable capital adequacy ratio.

- Cluster 3, consists of 51 topic items, namely: data analysis, analysis of the influence of capital adequacy ratio, analysis of third party funds, assets, independent banks, Indonesian people's banks, commercial banks, bei, operational costs operational income, Indonesian stock exchange, capital adequacy ratio, car, third party funds, panel data, deposit ratio, dpk, Indonesian securities, equity, evIEWS, financial report, firm size, independent variable, classic, credit, ldr, loan, month, npl, ldr, influence of car/dpk/loan, banking, performing loan, banking company, profitability, purposive sampling, quantitative data, ratio, return, roa, roe, significant to return, spss, state, data analysis techniques, third party fund, time series, f test, test t.
- Cluster 4, consists of 12 topic items, namely: bank size, data analysis method, Indonesian stock exchange, lar, loan deposit ratio, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, purposive sampling technique, ratio, sampling method, square.

Mapping Literature Review Studies regarding the Effect of Non-Performing Loans (NPL) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 47 influences of NPLs on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Reserve for impairment losses. NPLs can affect the size of the allowance for impairment losses. When banks have high NPLs, they must create larger reserves for impairment losses to anticipate possible losses from these NPLs. This can reduce bank profits and affect their financial growth.

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to bear credit risk and operational risk. If the NPL increases, the bank may experience a decrease in CAR because the bank has to spend more capital to form reserves for impairment losses. A decrease in CAR can reduce a bank's ability to provide loans and increase the risk of bankruptcy.

(3) Financial Distress. High NPLs can indicate larger financial problems at the bank. This may result in the bank's inability to meet its financial obligations, including repaying loans and maintaining minimum capital. If a bank experiences financial distress, the bank may experience the risk of bankruptcy.

(4) Financial Sustainability Ratio/FSR. FSR measures a bank's ability to meet its short-term and long-term obligations. If the NPL increases, the bank may experience a decrease in FSR because the bank must spend more capital to form reserves for impairment losses. A decrease in FSR can reduce investor confidence and affect the bank's reputation.

(5) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. High NPLs can affect a country's economic growth because they can reduce credit availability and worsen banking financial conditions. This can reduce investor confidence and affect economic growth. Conversely, low NPLs can support economic growth by increasing credit availability and increasing investor confidence.

(6) Share price. High NPLs can affect bank share prices because investors may consider the bank's high financial risks more. Additionally, banks that have high NPLs may experience a decline in earnings and financial performance, which can affect their stock prices.

(7) Amount of credit disbursed. High NPLs can affect a bank's ability to provide credit because banks must limit credit to reduce risk. This could have a negative impact on economic growth, especially if banks become less likely to lend money to productive sectors.

(8) Bank health. High NPLs can be a sign of larger financial problems at a bank and can affect their financial health. Banks that have high NPLs may have to establish larger impairment

loss reserves, which could reduce their profits and affect their growth. Apart from that, high NPLs can also cause banks to experience the risk of bankruptcy.

(9) Credit repayment capability. High NPLs can affect banks' ability to return credit that has been given to customers. This is because a high NPL indicates a greater risk of default, so banks must prepare larger capital reserves to overcome this risk. This can reduce banks' ability to provide new credit to customers who need it, because the capital required to handle NPLs must be maintained.

(10) Decision to grant credit. NPL also influences banking decisions in providing new credit to customers. Banks tend to be more careful in providing credit if the NPL is high, because the risk of default is greater. This can reduce the amount of credit provided by banks, which can affect economic growth.

(11) Investment decisions. NPL can also influence banking decisions in making investments. If the NPL is high, banks will be more inclined to retain their capital rather than invest it, because greater investment risk can increase the NPL and affect the bank's ability to repay the credit that has been provided. This can affect economic growth because investment is an important factor in economic development.

(12) Investment banking credit. NPLs can also affect investment banking credit. If the NPL is high, banks will be more inclined to provide investment credit to safer customers, with a lower risk of default. This can reduce the amount of investment credit provided by banks, which can affect economic growth.

(13) Company profits. A high level of NPL can affect a bank's financial performance, especially company profits. This is because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover losses from non-performing loans. This larger loss reserve will reduce the company's net profit and can reduce investor confidence in the bank's performance.

(14) Level of IPO Underpricing. IPO underpricing is the difference between the share offering price at the IPO and the share price at the initial offering. NPLs can influence underpricing levels because investors will be more wary of banks that have high NPL levels. Banks with high NPL levels will tend to have higher levels of underpricing because investors consider the risk of investing in these banks to be greater.

(15) Long term performance. A high NPL level can affect a company's long-term performance because it can reduce the bank's operational performance and reduce the quality of bank assets. Banks with high NPL levels may experience difficulty in obtaining capital and experience a reduced ability to provide credit. This can cause a decline in the company's long-term performance and reduce investor confidence in banks.

(16) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR is the ratio between the amount of credit provided by the bank and the amount of funds received from customers. NPLs can affect LDR because banks tend to reduce credit offers to avoid a higher risk of non-performing loans. This can reduce LDR and affect the bank's ability to expand business and provide credit to customers.

(17) Loan Loss Provision/LLP. LLP is a loss reserve created by the bank to cover possible losses that could result from non-performing loans. A high NPL level can affect LLPs because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This can reduce the bank's net profit and affect the company's liquidity.

(18) Net profit. A high NPL level can affect a bank's net profit because the bank must prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This will reduce bank revenues and affect the company's overall financial performance. Apart from that, a high NPL level can also affect investor confidence in bank performance and reduce the value of company shares.

(19) Liquidity. A high NPL level can affect a company's liquidity because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. These larger loss reserves can reduce bank liquidity and affect the bank's ability to fulfill payment obligations to customers.

(20) Earnings management. A high NPL level can affect a bank's profit management because the bank will try to manage the NPL level so that it is not too high and does not affect

the company's financial performance. This can affect the bank's financial reporting and pose a risk of violating applicable laws and regulations.

(21) Company value. A high NPL level can reduce company value because it indicates that the bank faces high credit risk and is likely to have to bear large losses in the future. This can reduce investor confidence in the company's performance and cause a decline in share prices.

(22) Net Interest Margin/NIM. NIM is the difference between interest income received by the bank and interest costs paid by the bank to customers. A high NPL level can affect NIM because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This can reduce bank interest income and reduce NIM.

(23) Net Profit Margin/NPM. NPM is the ratio between net profit and total bank income. A high NPL level can affect NPM because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This can reduce the bank's net profit and reduce NPM.

(24) Price Earning Ratio/PER. PER is the ratio between share price and company net profit. A high NPL level can affect PER because investors may assume that the bank faces high credit risk and is likely to have to bear large losses in the future. This can reduce bank share prices and reduce PER.

(25) Profit growth. NPLs can affect banking profit growth because banks have to prepare loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans, which can reduce the bank's net profit. Therefore, banks with lower NPL levels are better able to achieve higher profit growth than banks with higher NPL levels.

(26) Capital growth. A high NPL level can affect capital growth because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves, which can reduce profits that can be used to increase capital. Banks with lower NPL levels can more easily achieve higher capital growth than banks with higher NPL levels.

(27) Mudharabah Financing. NPLs can affect Mudharabah financing because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This can limit banks' ability to provide Mudharabah financing to customers, as banks must prioritize the use of funds to cover credit losses.

(28) Financing the Hajj bailout fund. NPLs can also affect the financing of Hajj bailout funds because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans. This could limit banks' ability to provide financing for Hajj bailouts, because banks must prioritize the use of funds to cover credit losses.

(29) Interest income. NPLs can affect banking interest income because banks must prepare loss reserves to cover the risk of non-performing loans, which can reduce bank interest income. Banks with lower NPL levels are better able to achieve higher interest income than banks with higher NPL levels.

(30) MSME credit distribution. NPLs can affect MSME credit distribution because banks will be more careful in channeling credit to the MSME sector if there is a high risk of non-performing loans. This can cause a decrease in MSME credit distribution and can affect the growth of the MSME sector.

(31) Distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR. NPLs can also affect the distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR because banks will be more careful in distributing credit to the MSME sector if there is a high risk of non-performing loans. This can cause a decrease in KUR distribution and can affect the growth of the MSME sector.

(32) Distribution of working capital credit. A high NPL level can affect the distribution of working capital loans because banks have to prepare larger reserves for losses, which can reduce profits that can be used to distribute working capital loans. This can limit the bank's ability to provide working capital credit to customers.

(33) Investment distribution. A high NPL level can affect investment distribution because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves, which can reduce profits that can be used to channel investment. This can limit the bank's ability to provide investments to customers.

(34) Distribution of consumption. A high NPL level can also affect consumption distribution because banks have to prepare larger loss reserves, which can reduce profits that can

be used to distribute consumption credit. This can limit banks' ability to provide consumer credit to customers.

(35) Distribution of Home/KAR Collateral Credit. NPLs can also affect KAR distribution because banks will be more careful in channeling credit to the property sector if there is a high risk of non-performing loans. This can cause a decrease in KAR distribution and can affect the growth of the property sector.

(36) Distribution of Home Ownership Credit/KPR. A high NPL can make it difficult for banks to distribute Home Ownership/KUR credit because banks will tend to be more careful in approving credit applications. Apart from that, high NPLs can also limit bank resources to distribute KUR credit because banks have to allocate more funds to handle existing problem loans.

(37) Qardhul Hasan Loan. A high NPL can make banks more careful in approving Qardhul Hasan loan applications because banks need to ensure that the party lending the money will be able to pay back according to the specified time period. Additionally, banks can also check a borrower's credit history before approving an application.

(38) Profitability. High NPLs can have a negative impact on bank profitability because banks need to allocate more funds to handle problem loans. In addition, if problem loans cannot be resolved properly, the bank may experience losses and reduce its net profit.

(39) Bank ratings. High NPL can affect a bank's rating because NPL is used as a financial indicator to assess bank performance. If the NPL is high, the bank's rating may decrease because NPL is considered a high credit risk which can have a negative impact on the bank's finances.

(40) Return On Assets/ROA. High NPLs can have a negative impact on ROA because banks have to allocate more funds to handle problem loans. This can reduce the bank's net profit and ultimately affect ROA. Apart from that, high NPLs can also make investors lose confidence in bank performance and ultimately affect ROA.

(41) Return On Equity/ROE. High NPL can affect ROE because ROE measures the net profit generated by the bank against the capital invested by shareholders. If banks have to allocate more funds to handle non-performing loans, the bank's net profit may decrease, thereby affecting ROE.

(42) Return On Investment/ROI. High NPL can affect ROI because ROI measures the return on investment obtained by investors. If banks have to allocate more funds to handle non-performing loans, the investment returns obtained by investors may decrease, thereby affecting ROI.

(43) Stock returns. High NPL can affect stock returns because stock returns measure the return on investment obtained by bank shareholders. If the NPL is high, the bank's net profit may decrease, so stock returns may also decrease.

(44) Shareholder Value. High NPLs can have a negative impact on shareholder value because NPLs indicate the credit risk faced by the bank. This can make investors lose trust in the bank and ultimately affect the bank's share price.

(45) Company debt level. High NPLs can affect a company's debt level because banks have to allocate more funds to handle problem loans. This can reduce the bank's ability to provide new loans and ultimately affect the company's debt levels.

(46) Level of cooperative credit health. High NPLs can affect the credit health of cooperatives because cooperatives often rely on loans from banks to run their operations. If banks experience credit problems, cooperatives may also experience difficulties in obtaining loans.

(47) Credit collectibility level. High NPLs can affect the level of credit collectibility because banks have to allocate more resources to collect problem loans. This can affect the collection process and ultimately affect the level of bank credit collectibility. In addition, if the NPL level is high, the risk of default can increase, thereby affecting the level of credit collectibility.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding Determinant Variables of Non-Performing Loans (NPL) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 47 NPL determinant variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. BOPO is a ratio that measures how much a bank's operational costs are compared to its operational income. The higher the BOPO, the greater the bank's operational costs compared to its operating income. If BOPO is high, it will be difficult for banks to earn sufficient profits to cover their operational costs. This can impact the bank's ability to manage credit risk and minimize NPLs.

(2) BI Rate. BI Rate is the interest rate set by Bank Indonesia as a reference for other banks in determining credit interest rates. If the BI Rate rises, credit interest rates will also rise, which can cause an increase in interest costs for customers who have credit. This can impact customers' ability to pay credit, which can increase credit risk and NPLs.

(3) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to meet the minimum capital requirements set by the regulator. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear risk and minimize NPLs. On the other hand, if the CAR is low, the bank will have limitations in bearing risk and increase credit risk and NPL.

(4) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. CSR is a company's social responsibility in carrying out its business activities responsibly towards the community and surrounding environment. If a bank carries out CSR well, it can increase public trust in the bank. This can have a positive impact on credit quality, because customers will have more trust and choose banks that carry out CSR well, so that it can help minimize credit risk and NPLs.

(5) Collectability. The level of Collectability or the customer's ability to repay their loans can affect the NPL level. The better the collectability level, the lower the likelihood of customers defaulting on their loans and therefore, the NPL level will tend to be lower.

(6) Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic can have a significant impact on NPL levels because it causes many businesses to close and increases the unemployment rate. This can lead to customers' inability to repay their loans, which in turn can increase the NPL level.

(7) Third Party Funds/DPK. A high level of deposits can help banks reduce NPL risk by providing a more stable and sustainable resource for lending money to customers. Conversely, if the DPK level is low, banks may experience difficulty in lending money, and in the end this can increase the risk of NPLs.

(8) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. The GDP level can influence the NPL level because it indicates the overall health of the economy. If GDP is low, there may be a decline in business and employment, which could cause customers to have difficulty repaying their loans. As a result, the NPL level may increase.

(9) Good Corporate Governance/GCG. A good level of GCG can help banks minimize NPL risk by increasing transparency, accountability and internal company supervision. This can help ensure that loans disbursed to customers have lower risks and can help reduce NPL levels.

(10) Inflation. The inflation rate can affect the NPL level because it can increase the cost of living and reduce purchasing power. This can cause customers to have difficulty paying their loans, which in turn can increase the NPL level.

(11) Interest Rate. Interest rates can affect NPL levels because they can affect customers' ability to repay their loans. If interest rates rise, loan payments become more expensive, and customers may have difficulty paying their loans. As a result, the NPL level may increase.

(12) Amount of credit disbursed. The NPL level can be influenced by the amount of credit disbursed by banks. If banks provide too many loans without considering the appropriate risks, then the NPL level can increase. Therefore, banks must carry out appropriate risk evaluations before providing loans to reduce the risk of NPLs.

(13) Debtor guarantee. Debtor guarantees can influence NPLs because they can minimize the credit risk taken by the bank. If a debtor provides collateral in the form of assets or securities, the bank can sell the collateral if the debtor is unable to pay the credit. Thus, bank credit risk is reduced and the possibility of NPLs also decreases.

(14) Inefficiency. Inefficiencies in banking operations can increase credit risk and the possibility of NPLs. Inefficiencies can occur in various ways, such as poor credit decision making

processes, lack of supervision of credit provided, or lack of effective credit risk management. Therefore, efficient banks tend to have lower NPL levels.

(15) Debtor characteristics. Debtor characteristics such as credit history, ability to pay, and income can influence the NPL level. If a debtor has a bad credit history or cannot pay his credit, then the possibility of NPLs will be higher. On the other hand, if the debtor has a good credit history and good ability to pay, then the possibility of NPLs will be lower.

(16) Company ownership. Company ownership can also influence NPLs in banking. If the bank is owned by the government, the credit risk can be lower because the government has large resources and can minimize the credit risk it takes. However, if the bank is owned by the private sector, the credit risk can be higher because the private sector has higher business risk.

(17) Credit policy. A loose credit policy can increase credit risk and the possibility of NPLs occurring. If a bank provides too much credit or with terms that are too easy, the credit risk will increase. Therefore, banks need to have strict credit policies and carefully assess the debtor's ability to repay credit.

(18) Capital adequacy. Capital adequacy is important for banks because it can affect the bank's ability to manage risks and bear losses due to NPLs. If the bank has sufficient capital, the bank can bear losses due to NPLs without experiencing serious financial problems. However, if the bank has insufficient capital, the bank can experience serious financial problems due to NPLs.

(19) Global crisis. The global crisis can affect the level of NPLs in banks because it can reduce economic performance and debtors' ability to pay credit. If a global crisis occurs, many companies and individuals may experience difficulty in paying their credit. Therefore, banks need to take preventive action and anticipate the possibility of NPLs resulting from the global crisis.

(20) Quality of Productive Assets/KAP. Productive Asset Quality (KAP) can affect NPLs in banking because poor KAP can increase credit risk and the possibility of NPLs occurring. A bad KAP can occur due to debtors being unable to pay credit, a decrease in the value of assets or securities, or other factors that affect the value of assets. Therefore, banks need to monitor KAP regularly and take action to reduce credit risk.

(21) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR is a ratio that measures the amount of loans provided by the bank compared to the amount of funds received from customers through deposits. If the LDR is too high, it means the bank is providing too many loans and not enough funds to cover the loans. This can increase credit risk and the possibility of NPLs occurring.

(22) Lapindo Mud. The Lapindo mudflow was a natural disaster that occurred in Sidoarjo, East Java in 2006. This disaster caused many companies and individuals to experience difficulties in paying their credit. Therefore, the Lapindo mudflow can affect NPLs in banking.

(23) Liquidity. Liquidity is a bank's ability to pay its financial obligations in the short term. If the bank does not have sufficient liquidity, the bank may experience difficulties in paying its obligations, including paying obligations to customers who make deposits. This can affect bank performance and increase the risk of NPLs.

(24) Credit risk management. Credit risk management is the process of measuring, controlling and monitoring credit risks faced by banks. If credit risk management is not good, the bank may experience difficulties in managing credit risk and minimizing the possibility of NPLs occurring.

(25) Qardhul Hasan contract management. Qardhul Hasan contract management is contract management which aims to avoid usury in banking transactions. If Qardhul Hasan contract management is not good, the bank may experience difficulties in managing credit risk and minimizing the possibility of NPLs occurring.

(26) Exchange rate/exchange rate. Exchange rates can affect the business and financial performance of a company, including banking. If there are significant exchange rate fluctuations, banks may experience difficulties in paying their obligations, especially on loans using foreign currency. This can affect bank performance and increase the risk of NPLs.

(27) Net Interest Margin/NIM. Net interest margin (NIM) is the difference between the interest income received by banks from loans and the interest costs paid to customers on their

deposits. If the NIM is low, the bank may experience difficulty in obtaining sufficient income to cover operational costs and manage credit risk. This can increase the risk of NPLs in banking.

(28) Payment Period. Payment period is the time period given by the bank to customers to pay their financial obligations. If the payment period is too long, the bank may experience difficulties in managing credit risk and minimizing the possibility of NPLs occurring.

(29) MSME credit distribution. MSME credit distribution can help increase economic growth and strengthen the base of small and medium businesses in Indonesia. However, MSME credit distribution also has risks that must be managed properly by banks. If banks do not have appropriate policies in managing credit risk for MSMEs, the risk of NPLs can increase.

(30) Providing Home Ownership Credit/KPR. Providing Home Ownership Credit/KPR can help increase people's access to decent housing. However, providing KPR also has risks that must be managed properly by the bank. If customers cannot pay mortgage installments on time, the risk of NPLs can increase.

(31) Providing Kupedes Credit. Kupedes Credit is credit given to customers to meet consumption or working capital needs. If the bank does not have appropriate policies in managing Kupedes credit risk, the NPL risk may increase.

(32) PSAK No. 50, 55, 71. PSAK No. 50, 55, and 71 regulate aspects of accounting and financial reporting in the banking sector. If banks do not apply accounting and financial reporting standards correctly, this can lead to errors in credit risk management. This can increase the risk of NPLs in banking.

(33) Gross Regional Domestic Product/GRDP. GRDP can be an important indicator in determining the performance of a region or country in terms of economic growth. An increase in GRDP can indicate that a region or country is experiencing positive economic growth, so that business and investment activities also increase. However, if there is a decline in GRDP, it will affect people's purchasing power so that it can trigger an increase in NPLs in the banking sector.

(34) Export growth. Export growth can be a factor that influences NPLs in banking. This is because poor export performance can reduce a company's income, thereby increasing the risk of unpaid credit. On the other hand, positive export growth can increase company income and reduce the risk of unpaid credit.

(35) Credit growth. Credit growth has a positive relationship with NPL. If credit growth is too high, it can increase the risk of NPLs. This happens because the more credit given, the greater the possibility of problematic credit. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to credit growth so that there is no significant increase in NPLs.

(36) Economic growth. Economic growth also has an influence on NPLs in banking. Increasing economic growth can increase people's income, so that the ability to pay credit increases. However, if economic growth decreases, people's ability to pay credit will also decrease, which can trigger an increase in NPLs in the banking sector.

(37) Growth of cooperatives. The growth of cooperatives can have a positive impact on NPLs in the banking sector. Cooperatives can be an alternative source of financing for small and medium enterprises (SMEs), so that they can help improve community welfare. In this way, the opportunity for bad credit to occur can be reduced.

(38) Working capital turnover. Working capital turnover can be a factor that influences NPL in banking. If working capital turnover is too low, it can increase the risk of NPLs. This is because the longer working capital is in circulation, the greater the possibility of problematic credit. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to working capital turnover so that there is no significant increase in NPL.

(39) Implementation of PNPM Mandiri Rural. Implementation of PNPM Mandiri Rural can have a positive impact on NPLs in the banking sector. This program provides support to rural communities to improve welfare, including through providing business capital. This can help people to earn more income so that the opportunity for bad credit can be reduced.

(40) Tax treatment. Tax treatment can have an influence on NPLs in banking. If taxes are too high, it can affect the profits obtained by the company, thereby increasing the risk of unpaid

credit. On the other hand, if taxes are low, the company will have more profits and can reduce the risk of unpaid credit.

(41) Financial ratios. Financial ratios such as the credit to deposit ratio, core capital to assets ratio, and profitability ratio can provide information regarding the financial health of banks. Poor financial ratios can indicate a higher NPL risk. For example, if the credit to deposit ratio is too high, this could indicate that the bank has borrowed too much and increases the risk of non-performing loans.

(42) CAMELS ratio. The CAMELS ratio includes Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management quality, Earnings, Liquidity, and Sensitivity to market risk. The CAMELS ratio is used to evaluate financial health and banking risk management. If a bank gets a poor score on several CAMELS components, this could indicate a higher NPL risk.

(43) Credit restructuring. Credit restructuring is a way to resolve problematic credit by changing the main conditions of the initially agreed credit. Credit restructuring can positively influence NPLs in banks if it is done correctly and on time. Credit restructuring can help reduce the number of problem loans and improve credit quality.

(44) Internal Control System. The internal control system includes policies, procedures and supervisory mechanisms implemented by banks to manage risks and ensure the company's financial integrity. A good internal control system can help reduce the risk of NPLs in banking by ensuring that the credit management process is carried out properly and is well controlled.

(45) Solvency. Solvency is a bank's ability to meet its financial obligations when they fall due. The higher a bank's solvency ratio, the greater its ability to overcome credit risk and handle problem loans. Therefore, the lower the bank's solvency ratio, the greater the possibility that the bank will experience problems in dealing with NPLs.

(46) Interest rates. Interest rates can affect NPLs in banking. The higher the interest rate, the higher the cost of capital for the borrower, and the greater the possibility of credit problems. Conversely, the lower the interest rate, the easier it is for borrowers to repay their credit and the smaller the possibility of NPLs occurring.

(47) Company size. Company size can also influence NPL in banking. Larger banks tend to have more resources to address credit risks and have more experience in managing non-performing loans. On the other hand, smaller banks tend to have a higher risk in managing non-performing loans.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2006 to 2022 which comes from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 750 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NPL ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 189 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 69 topics, cluster 2 consists of 57 topics, cluster 3 consists of 51 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 12 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 47 topics related to the influence of the NPL ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: reserves for impairment losses, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financial Distress, Financial Sustainability Ratio/FSR, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, share prices, amount of credit disbursed, health bank, credit repayment capability, credit granting decisions, investment decisions, investment banking credit, company profits, level of IPO Underpricing, long term performance, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Loan Loss Provision/LLP, net profit, liquidity, earnings management, company value, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Net Profit Margin/NPM, Price Earning Ratio/PER, profit growth, capital growth, Mudharabah financing, Hajj bailout financing, interest income, MSME credit distribution, People's Business Credit/KUR distribution, Distribution working capital credit, investment distribution, consumption distribution, Home Collateral Credit/KAR distribution, Home Ownership Credit/KPR distribution, Qardhul Hasan loans, profitability, bank rating, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, stock return,

shareholder value, company debt level, cooperative credit health level, and credit collectibility level.

Furthermore, there are 47 topics related to the determinants of the NPL ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO, BI rate, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, Collectability, Covid-19, Party Funds Third/DPK, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, inflation, interest rate, amount of credit disbursed, debtor guarantees, inefficiency, debtor characteristics, company ownership, credit policy, capital adequacy, global crisis, Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Lapindo mud, liquidity, credit risk management, Qardhul Hasan contract management, exchange rate, Net Interest Margin/NIM, payment period, MSME credit distribution, Home Ownership Credit/KPR, Credit provision KUPEDES, PSAK No. 50, 55, 71, Gross Regional Domestic Product/GRDP, export growth, credit growth, economic growth, cooperative growth, working capital turnover, implementation of PNPM Mandiri Rural, tax treatment, financial ratios, CAMELS ratio, credit restructuring, Internal Control System, solvency, interest rates, and company size.

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